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To cite this article: Krystallia Dimitriadou *et al* 2024 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2767** 042010

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Quality assessment of the GPM IMERG product for lifetime prediction of turbine blades in complex terrain

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Abstract. Wind turbine blades may suffer leading edge erosion when rain hits the blades extremely fast, resulting in blade damage that will negatively impact power production. Since wind turbines are growing in size, this translates into higher tip speeds when the blades rotate and, therefore, are more prone to erosion. Wind turbines in mountainous terrain may also suffer erosion due to the high winds and precipitation rates. Therefore, it becomes important to estimate blade lifetimes in wind farm sites with terrain complexity. Blade lifetime prediction models utilize a time series of rainfall intensity, wind speeds, and a turbine-specific tip speed curve. In our study, we assess the quality of the Integrated Multi-satellite Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) final product in a blade lifetime prediction model for a mountainous area during the period 2015-2020. We first compare the IMERG rainfall intensities against in situ observations at 28 stations in Navarra in Northern Spain. We find that the two datasets are closer to agreement when the rainfall intensities are aggregated in monthly rather than 30-minute temporal scales with correlation coefficients between 0.74 - 0.93. We calculate the average annual rainfall in the period, and we find that IMERG over(under)estimates precipitation in 15 (8) stations, in line with previous studies that have pinpointed the limitations of IMERG in complex terrain. We then input the 30-minute IMERG, in situ rainfall intensities, and the 30-minute New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) wind speeds, extracted at each station location and interpolated at 119 m height, into a blade lifetime model. Our results indicate blade lifetimes of 6-17 years in 13 stations, with the in situ data to provide, on average, longer estimates than the IMERG product. Despite the limitations, we conclude that the satellite-based precipitation from IMERG may become a useful dataset for the lifetime estimation of wind turbine blades in complex terrain, with calibration and adjustments of the IMERG data.

1. Introduction

Leading Edge Erosion (LEE) can be a significant challenge in wind turbines since it can negatively impact the efficiency, performance, and durability of the turbine blades. The shape and smoothness of the blade's leading edge are crucial for maintaining optimal aerodynamic performance. Erosion can disrupt the smooth airflow over the blade, leading to increased drag and reduced efficiency. As erosion progresses, the overall efficiency of the wind turbine decreases. The roughening of eroded blades generates less lift and more drag, which can result

in a reduction in power output. This directly impacts the amount of electricity that the wind turbine can generate, leading to lower energy production and potentially affecting the economic viability of the turbine. Erosion can compromise the structural integrity of the blades over time. The loss of material from the leading edge can weaken the blade's overall strength and stiffness. This could lead to fatigue, cracks, and even blade failure. The costs associated with repairing or replacing eroded wind turbine blades can be substantial. If erosion-related issues are not managed effectively, they can impact the overall financial performance of the wind farm [1, 2, 3].

The combination of intense rainfall and strong winds can significantly harm wind turbine blades through leading-edge erosion. Notably, hail poses a pronounced erosion threat [2, 4]. As operational wind turbines increase in size and blade length, the LEE effect will be amplified due to higher wind speed, impacting blade longevity and annual energy output. Given the substantial expenses associated with repairs and maintenance, it is imperative to proactively address erosion risks during wind farms' initial design and planning stages.

Rain and hail-induced leading edge erosion is a concern for wind turbine operators, especially in regions prone to severe rain and hailstorms. Addressing this challenge is crucial to ensure the efficient and safe operation of wind turbines and to maximize their lifespan and energy production. Understanding the meteorological factors that contribute to leading-edge erosion is essential for developing effective erosion mitigation strategies and ensuring the long-term performance and durability of wind turbines.

Satellites can provide global or regional coverage, allowing for a comprehensive view of rainfall patterns across various wind farms and geographic areas, including areas where in situ measurements are sparse or unavailable. Due to satellites' continuous monitoring, they are able to track rainfall patterns over different timescales, from short-duration events to long-term trends.

The Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) mission, launched in 2014, is an international satellite-based initiative designed to enhance our understanding of global precipitation patterns. GPM involves a constellation of satellites equipped with advanced instruments such as dual frequency radars operating in Ku-band (13.6 GHz) and Ka-band (35.5 GHz) along with the GPM Microwave Imager, which covers frequencies in the range 10-183 GHz [5]. By collecting data from various sources, GPM creates a comprehensive and unified global precipitation dataset covering hail, heavy and light rainfall, and snow.

The Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) offers a variety of precipitation products tailored to different timeframes and purposes. These products include the IMERG Early, Late, and Final versions. The Early and Late versions have a latency of 4 and 14 hours, respectively, and have forward propagation. Their main difference is that the Late version has backward propagation and includes the lagging transmission. The IMERG Final product is considered the most appropriate for research purposes since it is calibrated according to monthly rain gauge data [6]. IMERG covers an area from 60°N to 60°S latitude, a uniform grid spacing of 0.1°, and a temporal resolution of 30 min. Several studies have attributed to assessing the performance of GPM IMERG; a summary of them can be found in [7]. Of particular interest are the studies of [8] [9] and [10], who conduct a performance assessment of the IMERG product(s) over Ebro Valey, Catalonia and the whole Spain, respectively, revealing the usefulness of the satellite product and its challenges in the orographic precipitation. Furthermore, the authors of [11] showed that rainfall intensities from the GPM IMERG Final product can be utilized as input in a blade lifetime prediction model and, therefore, proven useful for predicting blade erosion.

Inspired by the suggestions of [11], we expand the methodology in a wind turbine test site located at a high altitude and complex terrain characterized by high precipitation rates. The test site is located in Northern Spain, one of the country's most rainy regions, with precipitation that surpasses 1500 mm per year. This is attributed to the convective rain related to mesoscale

components and the orographic forcing by the Pyrenees and the Cantarian mountains [10]. We hypothesize that IMERG rainfall intensities could be utilized for the prediction of erosion damage on wind turbine blades in complex terrain. We will first evaluate rainfall intensities from the IMERG Final product against in situ observations from 28 meteorological stations in Northern Spain. The meteorological stations are distributed around and near the area of interest in height elevations from 125 to 1353 m. We then input the IMERG rainfall intensities and the in situ observations to a lifetime prediction model of wind turbine blades and compare the two lifetime estimations.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Studied area

Navarra is a region where the combination of topographic complexity and climatic conditions is a challenge for the remote sensing estimation of precipitation from satellite or ground-based products.

The area of study is located in the north of the Iberian Peninsula with approximately 10.400 km², where the orography of the region shows a variety of rich features broadly limited by two large mountain systems: the Iberic System in the South of Navarra and the Pyrenees in the North, which merge westward with the last foothills of the Cantabrian Mountains. Between them, the Ebro Valley crosses the region from northwest to southwest toward the Mediterranean. A closer look at the Navarre reveals a complex array of smaller mountain systems and valleys (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Digital elevation model of Navarra and *Meteo Navarra* stations network distribution.

The variety and richness of climatic nuances is the main characteristic of Navarre's climate. Most of the climates of the Iberian Peninsula can be identified in this area. The Cantabrian valleys have a temperate and humid climate, with cloudiness and abundant rainfall. On the

contrary, in the southern part, the continental, arid, and dry Mediterranean climate of the Navarrese Ribera makes its appearance, which, in the Bardenas, acquires desert features. And between both environments, Cantabrian valleys and Ribera, a wide variety of different nuances appear. To the south of the Belate-Azpirotz dividing chain, some features of the oceanic climate still persist in the humid southern valleys (Basaburua, Ultzama, Juslapeña). In the Pamplona and Lumbier-Aoiz Basins, the sub-oceanic and sub-Mediterranean characteristics come together, and Middle Navarra, south of the outer mountain ranges, presents Mediterranean characteristics but with more abundant rainfall than the Ribera. This varied climatic framework is completed by the subalpine climate of the Pyrenean valleys, with more extreme thermal conditions and abundant precipitation in the form of snow.

2.2. Satellite observations

The satellite data used for our study is the GPM IMERG Final Precipitation L3 Half Hourly product version V06B (IMERG-F V06B). The IMERG-F data have a spatial and temporal resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ and 30 min, respectively, and is recommended for research purposes since it has undergone a monthly gauge adjustment with inputs from the Global Precipitation Climatology Center (GPCC) [6]. Our study period covers the years 2015-2020.

2.3. In situ observations

The GPM IMERG Final Precipitation L3 Half Hourly product was validated by taking as a reference meteorological data from the automatic stations of the meteorological network of Navarra [12]. 28 meteorological stations from this network (<http://meteo.navarra.es/>), at 10 m height, have been used. Figure 1 shows their geographical distribution. Ten minutes of precipitation, were obtained in UTC between 1 January 2015 and 31 December 2023. Since the in situ data was delivered every 10 minutes, we calculated the cumulative values over 30-minute intervals to match the IMERG temporal resolution.

2.4. Data filtering and quality control

The data used from the IMERG product was the `precipitationCal`, which refers to the calibration precipitation estimate from the various infrared and microwave satellite sensors. To ensure sufficient data quality, precipitation data were excluded whenever their `precipitationQualityIndex` was less than 0.4 [6]. Also, since we are interested in assessing the impact of rain on wind turbine blades, the solid precipitation, such as hail, graupel, or snow, needed to be removed from the dataset. The authors of [13] indicated that the empirical threshold of the IMERG parameter `probabilityLiquidPrecipitation` for classifying precipitation as rain or snow is 50%. Following the same method as [11], we increased this threshold and kept precipitation data with `probabilityLiquidPrecipitation` larger than 75% in order to exclude graupel and hail. Finally, as the minimum rainfall, we have considered `precipitationCal` values equal or greater than 0.2 mm/h (0.1 mm/30 min) [14]. We have kept only the corresponding in situ data to the filtered satellite ones for consistency. Natively, IMERG `precipitationCal` data are provided in mm/hour, but after the quality control and filtering, we converted them to half-hourly accumulated rainfall (mm/30 min).

2.5. IMERG data evaluation

We assessed the performance of IMERG by comparing it with in situ measurements in different temporal scales. The performance metrics used for the evaluation were the correlation coefficient (R) and the mean bias (B), based on existing validation methods [9, 15]. They were calculated for each station based on the equations (1) - (2) given below:

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (R_{\text{IMERG},i} - \bar{R}_{\text{IMERG}}) (R_{\text{In situ},i} - \bar{R}_{\text{In situ}})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (R_{\text{IMERG},i} - \bar{R}_{\text{IMERG}})^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (R_{\text{In situ},i} - \bar{R}_{\text{In situ}})^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$B = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (R_{\text{IMERG},i} - R_{\text{In situ},i}) \quad (2)$$

where $R_{\text{IMERG},i}$ and $R_{\text{In situ},i}$ reflect the rainfall accumulation in the temporal scales of 30 min, hourly, daily and monthly for the IMERG and in-situ data, respectively, while n represents the sample size covering the whole studied period.

2.6. NEWA wind speed data

Since the stations are located in a complex terrain affected by mesoscale weather phenomena and orographic effects, we used NEWA project [16] wind speeds as the best approximation of wind conditions at hub heights of wind turbines in the area. The wind speeds were extracted at each station every 30 minutes for the period 2015-2020 and at heights of 100 and 150 m. Note that this study uses recently produced NEWA data beyond 2018.

2.7. Rain erosion damage model

In our study, we model the gradual leading-edge erosion damage caused by the impingement of precipitation during turbine operation. The impingement damage model is detailed in [17] and [18]. The model is based on data from a Rain Erosion Tester (RET) by R&D Test Systems A/S, where blade specimens are exposed to water droplets of various sizes dispensed by needles. The onset time of erosion, or incubation time, is determined by visual inspections of images taken during these tests, tracking the initial failure of the protective coating, which typically starts near the high-speed rotor tip. For damage calculations using meteorological data, we convert rainfall data to impinged water (H) at the tip of the blade, taking into account rainfall intensity and fall velocity of rain droplets. The fall velocity of the rain droplets is derived from empirical relations described in [19]. In our study, the DTU 10 MW reference wind turbine [20] is used for all calculations. The NEWA wind speed is extrapolated to the hub height of the DTU 10 MW wind turbine, which is 119 m. Extrapolation is done with the power law, where the shear exponent is evaluated for each time step with wind speed data at 100 and 150 m. The hub height wind speed is then converted into wind turbine blade's tip speed, where the tip speed is based on a curve as a function of wind speed at hub height. Our damage calculations follow the Palmgren-Miner rule to estimate the accumulated damage, indicating the onset of rain erosion and initial coating failure.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. IMERG data validation in different temporal scales

We, hereby, present the results from the comparison between the IMERG and the in situ rainfall intensities. We assessed the agreement of the two datasets in half-hourly (IMERG's native resolution), hourly, daily and monthly temporal resolutions for the studied period. We calculated the respective correlation coefficients and mean biases for each station.

Table 1 shows the range of the correlation coefficient (R_{min} - R_{max}) for all the stations in the different temporal scales. It is clearly evident that the detection performance/accuracy of IMERG improves with a coarser temporal aggregation of the rainfall since R has a range of 0.18-0.34 for 30-minute rainfall intensities while 0.74-0.93 for monthly rainfall accumulations. This means that the rainfall data in the two datasets exhibit a stronger correlation when aggregated over longer time intervals. Coarser temporal scales (e.g. daily, monthly) can mitigate the impact

of short-term variability and average out extreme values that rainfall datasets often demonstrate. In addition, the IMERG data undergo a monthly GPCP gauge adjustment, resulting in better correlation in monthly scales between the datasets than daily and sub-daily scales [6, 21, 7].

Table 1. IMERG vs. In Situ correlation coefficient ranges (all stations) for rainfall accumulations in different temporal scales.

Time scale	R_{min}	R_{max}
half-hourly	0.18	0.34
hourly	0.33	0.46
daily	0.62	0.79
monthly	0.74	0.93

On the other hand, the bias measures the average error between the IMERG and the in situ data for all 28 stations. Our results indicate that IMERG systematically overestimates rainfall in 17 stations (SA, TM, CA, TA, PG, BY, YE, ES, VY, AO, CR, BO, BL, AC, UJ, EP, AG) and underestimates in 6 stations (DO, BE, EL, UR, ER, GO) for all temporal aggregations (results not shown). This result aligns with many previous IMERG studies, which indicated substantial over or underestimation of orographic precipitation in mountainous regions in Spain [22, 8, 10, 9] and around the world [7]. The positive biases for the 17 stations are on average 0.20, 0.44, 2.15, and 14.78 mm, and the negative biases for the 6 stations are on average -0.11, -0.16, -2.30 and -34.27 mm (half-hourly, hourly, daily and monthly scales). In most of the stations (23/28), the bias gets more significant (regardless of the direction of systematic error) with the coarser temporal aggregation. This may be attributed to the fact that monthly scales may include seasonal variations. Previous IMERG studies have shown discrepancies in winter precipitation [23, 7], and studies over Spain have spotted an overestimation of IMERG rainfall during summer and autumn due to high convective activity [8, 10]. When interpreting the bias, we must also consider its limitations, such as the cancellation of positive and negative errors between the two datasets and its influence by outlier values.

Figure 2 illustrates the average annual rainfall of IMERG and the in situ observations for the 28 stations, which are sorted according to their elevation height (lower to higher elevation). The NEWA mean wind speed at 119 m during the period 2015-2020 for each station is overlaid on top. The GO, BE, and DO are the stations with the highest annual average rainfall of more than 1500 mm and the most significant discrepancies between IMERG and in situ data. These stations are within close proximity to the coast (see Figure 1), and they are likely affected first by the advection of wet maritime air masses from the Atlantic ocean [8].

Similarly to the positive biases of the daily and monthly rainfall aggregations, the IMERG mean annual rainfall exceeds the respective rainfall observed on the ground during the 6 years, albeit in 15 instead of 17 stations. This is mostly noticed in stations with elevation heights between 314 m (SA) and 1024 m (EL). On the contrary, the IMERG tends to underestimate rainfall in stations with the lowest elevation (DO - 125 m, BE - 306 m) and in most stations with the highest elevation (>1000 m). The latter aligns with the works of [24, 22, 9] for mountainous areas in Cyprus, the Alps and Pyrenees and Catalonia, respectively.

The NEWA mean wind speeds at 119 m height and for the period 2015-2020 span from 4.7 m/s to 8.8 m/s. In the majority of stations (19/28), the NEWA mean wind speed at 119 m exceeds 6 m/s with the highest values of 8.6 m/s and 8.3 m/s at the stations TI and CR, respectively. The mean wind speeds do not seem to follow a clear positive linear relationship with the elevation height.

The overall comparison of the IMERG rainfall versus the Navarra rain gauge data confirms the outcomes of previous studies assessing precipitation in the Northern Spain [22, 8, 10, 9]. The observed discrepancies may arise due to the area's climate in combination with the limitations of the two datasets and their different detection principle. Navarra has a strong spatial heterogeneity that may challenge satellite products and ground instruments. The local climate is affected by large-scale atmospheric circulations interacting with an orographically complex terrain. The IMERG product encompasses measurements of air volumes from infrared and microwave sensors, while rain gauges measure the weight of rain droplets at specific point locations. Also, rain gauges data may include wind-induced biases since due to evaporation loss.

Figure 2. Average annual rainfall from IMERG and in situ data (bars) and average NEWA mean wind speed at 119 m (black curve) during the period 2015-2020 for the 28 investigated stations. The stations are sorted according to their elevation height (low to high), and the vertical dotted lines display the reference heights at 300, 500, and 1000 m.

3.2. Estimation of erosion onset time

Figure 3 illustrates the expected onset time of erosion in years per station, calculated with input from the 30-minute rainfall from IMERG and the in situ measurements, and the 30-minute mean NEWA winds. We first observe that, in 15 stations, the lifetimes extend beyond the typical lifetime of a blade (25 years). Leading edge erosion can occur in the presence of heavy rain and strong winds [3, 2]. Therefore, we assume that these stations may not experience large amounts of rain and strong winds at the same time throughout the studied period. A future in-depth evaluation of rain occurrences and investigation of the wind data in the rainy periods may shed more light on this. Another possible explanation could be that the stations are located in an orographically complex area, which may act as a wind or rain shelter for some stations. The authors of [2] noted that using a time series shorter than 10 years may cause a larger uncertainty in the calculated blade lifetimes, which may also be a possible scenario to our findings.

Second, we see that in 13 stations, the model predicts blade lifetimes below 23 and 17 years, with inputs from the in situ and IMERG data, respectively. It is obvious that in most stations (10/13), the in situ data indicate dryer conditions than the respective IMERG data, thus translating into longer blade lifetimes. These differences can also be attributed to the observed discrepancies between the IMERG and the in situ data (see section 3.1). The most

severe cases are in stations ER, TI, and GE, with blade lifetimes between 6 and 9 years. It is worth mentioning that these stations have very high NEWA mean wind speeds for the period 2015-2020 of 7.6, 8.6, and 7.8 m/s, confirming the key role of wind in erosion of blades. At this point, it is important to stress that the NEWA data set may also introduce some bias to our calculations. The NEWA model chain consists of a downscaling process from the ERA5 wind climatology to the WRF mesoscale model and finally to the Wind Atlas Analysis and Application Program (WAsP) microscale model. The authors of [25] evaluated this model chain against 291 masts in Europe, finding that in simple orography, the downscaling of WRF wind climates using WAsP reduced the mean wind speed bias and spread to 0.05 ± 0.49 m/s, but in complex terrain, WAsP resulted in overestimations of the mean wind speed due to the orographic speed-up induced by the steep terrain.

Navarra has a total of 1355 MW of wind energy installed, translated to 58 wind farms with more than 1100 wind turbines with powers between 500 and 600 kW and hub heights between 40 and 60 m with a tip speed of 61 m/s. The most recent parks have wind turbines of up to 3 MW with hub heights of up to 120 m and tip speeds up to 92 m/s [26]. In our analysis, we have used the DTU 10 MW reference wind turbine with a hub height at 119 m and with maximum tip speed of 89.9 m/s, which represents the current and future trends in wind turbine sizes and also the new installations in Navarra. Therefore, wind turbines with lower tip speeds may suffer less erosion than those with higher tip speeds, so our results indicate an erosion criticality for the new installations.

Figure 3. Blade lifetimes estimated using 30 min accumulated rainfall intensities from IMERG and the in situ data. Note that some stations exceed the current blade life time expectancy (25 years).

4. Conclusions

Surface erosion of wind turbine blades is caused by heavy precipitation and strong winds and represents a major challenge in the wind energy industry. We have demonstrated that IMERG rainfall observations from the GPM satellite mission can be utilized as input for a blade lifetime prediction model in the orographically complex area of Navarra in Spain. We first compared IMERG against in situ rainfall in 28 stations in Navarra at half-hourly, hourly, daily, and monthly scales, and we found that the agreement between the datasets increases when aggregating them

in longer time periods. The comparison of the average annual rainfall between IMERG and in situ data during the period 2015-2020, revealed an over and underestimation of the rainfall in 15 and 8 stations, respectively, in line with previous studies.

We conclude that the IMERG final product requires additional calibration and adjustments in order to better represent rainfall variability in complex terrain, since its accuracy is linked to the rain climate of the region. We also find that the 30 min resolution of IMERG and in situ measurements in combination with NEWA winds at a reference hub height of 119 m predict blade lifetimes from 6 to 17 years in 13 stations, thus underlying the erosion criticality in the area. The NEWA winds represented a suitable option for the wind regime at hub heights, but in the future such a study would benefit from direct wind observations at hub heights. The comparison of the two sets of results may reveal useful insights both for the erosion and for the modelled winds. Future research on more wind farm test sites and in different climate regimes may shed more light to IMERG's capabilities in the prediction of erosion in blades. Finally, we conclude that the IMERG product needs further calibration and verification in complex terrain before it can be used to assess blade lifetimes in mountainous regions.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank the AIRE project, which has received funding from the European Union under the grant agreement 101083716. We also thank the NEWA team at DTU Wind and Energy Systems for providing the NEWA data tailored to our study.

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